

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KARIRI****FIRST NAME: KUDZAYI****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 6-12)
2. American vs. British (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
3. Punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. Style Guides (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)
6. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2024, 58-64)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Before taking the ACA-401D course, I believed I had a strong understanding of essay writing, having completed two master's theses; this course has broadened my horizons, particularly in areas I had previously taken for granted. My day-to-day work involves drafting various documents, presentations, and reports; however, with this course, I have come to recognize that academic writing requires close attention to details, such as acknowledging others' work, style, and language to ensure clarity, consistency, and credibility. The most notable aspects I have learned are punctuation, avoiding plagiarism, consistent use of style guides, distinguishing between American and British English, and limited use of Latin abbreviations and expressions. I now understand that each element is crucial in shaping effective academic writing and communication.

In this response paper, I reflect on the lecture, highlighting the key takeaways and areas of personal relevance.

2) **BODY**

I have selected the following areas that resonate with me when I reflect on the course.

a) Essay Writing

The first chapter of the ACA-401D course pack for period one, on essay writing, provides valuable insights into crafting effective essays. Structure, clarity, and evidence, as well as acknowledging the work of others, are indispensable tools for any academic essay to provide an answer to a question or a task using evidence (EUCLID 2024, 7).

In academic essay writing, credibility hinges on using sound evidence supported by much reading and research. Through this course, I have realized the importance of a good, balanced academic essay highlighting different sources, key arguments, and relevant aspects (EUCLID 2024, 9).

Reflecting on the importance of editing has surprised me as I often rush to complete a document, leaving little time for editing. The course pack recommendation of keeping some editing time has changed how I structure or plan my writing. Indeed, proper editing improves the flow of essays dramatically.

Reflecting on the importance of essay writing, I realize that I can only improve through revision and practice. As I strive to enhance my academic essay-writing skills, I will keep these principles at the forefront of my work.

b) American Vs. British English

Through the ACA-401D course pack, I have realized that the tone and language used in essay writing are closely linked to the quality of the essay. As someone educated in the British Education System, I typically use British English in my written work. However, due to varying Information and Communication Technology (ICT) configurations in different institutions, I tend to mix British and American spellings within the same document over time. Additionally, I mix different terms, concepts, or expressions when speaking, which influences my writing. This course taught me the importance of consistency in using the same language terms, spellings, and style (EUCLID 2024, 28). This consistency is crucial when writing in educated and scientific English, as the two versions of English are more similar than different (EUCLID 2024, 25).

This course has emphasized the importance of paying attention to spelling, vocabulary, and grammar differences to ensure clarity and consistency.

c) Punctuation

Unlike other writings, in academic essay writing, punctuation ensures meaning and clarity, reducing misunderstanding and misinterpretation of ideas. However, overuse of punctuation can also result in opposite intentions; EUCLID (2024, 16) recommends a rule of thumb to use as little punctuation as possible.

The course pack also highlights that punctuation, such as quotation marks, is influenced by the language being used, for example, British English vs American English. It is thus important to pay attention to both the type of English and punctuation in academic writing.

d) Plagiarism

According to EUCLID (2024, 34), plagiarism is using someone's work or ideas by quoting, paraphrasing, copying, or pasting without acknowledging the source of the information (EUCLID 2024, 34). Good essays must employ proper citation practices, whether paraphrasing, copying, summarizing, or directly quoting sources.

There are two methods used in academic essays to acknowledge the work of others: in-text – “citing the piece of work you are using within the actual text itself” citation and list of works cited- “bibliography or the references listed at the end of the book” (EUCLID 2024, 35).

e) Style Guides

EUCLID (2024, 41) defines style guides as a means of documenting basic rules or features to ensure consistency, providing a standardized framework for academic essays. Styles are broader than mere punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary but can encompass aspects such as structure, manuscript layout, font usage, use of abbreviations, symbols, voice preferences (active vs. passive), etc. (EUCLID 2024, 41). This list is dependent on the writer, publication company, or academic field.

I have noted that there are several style guides with examples, such as the Economist style guide, BBC News style guide, and the Chicago Manual of Style, which provide guidance to ensure consistency in language use, citation, and formatting, which is crucial for readability and communication (EUCLID 2024, 42).

I have noted that EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) and American English, though other internationally recognized styles available are acceptable (EUCLID 2024, 41). Styles guides are important, among other things to ensure clarity, consistency, and collaboration with other writers (EUCLID 2024, 41). The provision of templates by EUCLID goes a long way in ensuring that my writing will be consistent and follow an expected format or layout.

f) Latin Abbreviations and Expressions

One area of this period of the ACA-401D course is the use of Latin abbreviations and expressions in academic essay writing, especially for someone with an economics academic background where such terms as ‘ceteris paribus’ are commonly used. I have always believed that academics use Latin words and abbreviations to sound sophisticated; however, I note that chapter seven of the ACA-401D course pack, period one recommends limiting their use and instead using English equivalents to avoid misinterpretation, especially in business, formal, and technical writing (EUCLID 2024, 59).

The provision of the two tables in chapter seven of the ACA 401d course pack will go a long way in ensuring that I stick to using simple English equivalents to Latin expressions and words.

3) CONCLUSION

In the pursuit of academic excellence, writing a well-crafted essay is an acquired cornerstone skill. My takeaways from this lecture underscore that punctuation, plagiarism, style guides, language variations, and Latin expressions are fundamental aspects of academic writing that improve clarity and consistency. Reflecting on the lecture, I find that I will have to hone these skills through practice and revision to improve my essay writing.

I am confident that my essay writing will become clearer, impactful, and meaningful. The principles and insights shared have already inspired me to approach future assignments with a more thoughtful and deliberate mindset.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.